

Changing times, changing places

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More and more importance is being placed on the mobility of researchers in Europe, especially early in their careers. The challenges faced by young mobile researchers were the subject of a recent conference in Lisbon.

Research, according to the Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary, is *investigation or experimentation aimed at the discovery and interpretation of facts, revision of accepted theories or laws in the light of new facts, or practical application of such new or revised theories or laws.*

This concept has changed little since the days of the early scholars. What has evolved over the course of time, however, is the way in which research is conducted, with increasing emphasis on collaborations and interactions across the borders between nations as well as between disciplines. Young researchers are increasingly encouraged to be mobile, to cultivate teamwork and to be open to interdisciplinary approaches. While developing excellence in their primary field of interest, they are also expected to keep an eye on progress in neighbouring fields and to develop an awareness of potential synergies with other research areas.

A growing number of fellowships are geared towards young researchers, giving them the opportunity for training and work experience outside their home country or in the commercial sector. These mobility schemes are essential for the dissemination of knowledge and help researchers to find their place in the changing scientific labour market on a European scale.

It is never too late to get moving. If planned carefully, researchers at practically any stage of their careers can benefit from the experience of working in a new country, discipline or sector. Employers and policy makers are attaching particular value, however, to early career mobility. Young people are usually very enthusiastic about their work, they are eager to try out new things and embark on projects that do not have a

predefined outcome. They can also move around the world much more easily than later in their careers, when both family and professional obligations can create considerable constraints. Indeed, our knowledge-gear society is based very much on the presence of this dynamic research population, able to master and produce new knowledge for the benefit of society at large.

The chance of a lifetime

“Interaction with brilliant researchers and contacts with a different culture and language are among the greatest benefits any young researchers can be given!” says Marco Dorigo, a fellow in the European Commission (EC)’s Marie Curie fellowship scheme, summarising in a few words what many participants in the European mobility programmes have experienced (see *Marie Curie Fellowships – Success Stories*, Published by the European Commission, December 1997). The stay at the foreign institution was, for them, an important stepping stone in the development of their careers. This was certainly the case for Marco: he now holds a permanent position at his former host institution and was awarded one of the Marie Curie Excellence Awards in 2003 for his outstanding research achievements after the fellowship.

For many researchers, being mobile is the only way to acquire access to the research facilities and infrastructures they need to excel in their field, or to work with world experts in their research area. However, the benefits go far beyond that, especially for researchers who are not yet at an advanced career stage. Being integrated in a multinational and multicultural environment typically leads to early scientific maturity and independence and to a broader way of thinking. People learn to be flexible and open-minded and to adapt easily to new situations and global structures. While acquiring scientific knowledge without borders and constraints, their work also becomes significantly more visible. At the same time, being familiar with modern tools and technologies they make an invaluable contribution

to bridging the gap between different disciplines and sectors, and also between different generations of researchers.

Just pack your bags and go? It's not that easy...

Being mobile at an early stage may be easy in some respects but certainly not in all. Many young researchers are not aware of the opportunities that are available in terms of funding, and often they do not yet have the professional contacts necessary to set up short-term stays abroad, which are mostly based on personal contacts. This is particularly true for many Eastern European countries, where not only access to information can be a problem, but also traditional and sometimes hierarchical research structures can make it difficult for a young person to go abroad with an option to return.

The basic problem of a lack of adequate information was pointed out by various speakers at the recent conference *ESRM2004: Early Stage Researcher Mobility in Europe – Meeting the Challenges and Promoting Best Practice* (held in Lisbon (Portugal), 25–27 February 2004). The conference, which was jointly organized by Euroscience, the Marie Curie Fellowship Association, Eurodoc and PI-net, looked very closely at the obstacles encountered by mobile researchers, but it also highlighted a range of initiatives that are currently in progress to improve the situation.

The conference was attended by close to 180 researchers, policy makers, funding providers and research administrators from all over Europe and beyond, demonstrating the growing interest in the topic of early career mobility.

Among the major concerns of early stage researchers is the frequent lack of appropriate social security benefits. While provisions for health insurance are usually made (although not always at a satisfactory level), provisions for pension contributions and other social benefits vary from minimal to non-existent and are rarely harmonised at an international level. This can lead to severe problems for researchers who spend relatively short periods of time (one or two years) in several countries, especially when it comes to pension schemes. They often have to contribute to schemes from which they may not be able to benefit later on, or they may not be integrated into a pension scheme at all.

Lisbon's Gulbenkian Museum is set in luxuriant gardens

Even if early career researchers are often single and relatively independent, a significant number of mobile young researchers do have a family to take into account, and finding suitable day-care facilities is just one issue that can make mobility very difficult. Female researchers are particularly vulnerable to problems of this type, which, in combination with the traditional expectation that women absorb a bigger load of child-care and housework, results in their dropping out of research in significantly higher numbers than men.

Don't despair – there's hope for improvement!

To address the need for more centralised and easily accessible information on available fellowship and job opportunities, and also on questions related to visas, social security rights, fiscal matters and practical aspects of everyday life in a foreign country, the EC has set in train two new initiatives. The first, the Researcher's Mobility Portal, went online last summer (see *The European Researcher's Mobility Portal: a gateway to new opportunities* in this issue), and new functions are constantly being added. Besides offering a host of essential and reliable information for mobile researchers, it also gives the opportunity to post your CV and to search up-to-date job adverts in research-related fields.

The second initiative, which is closely related, is a network of Mobility Centres, which will be officially launched in June and will provide personalised assistance to researchers and their families in all countries of the European Union (EU) and associated states. For researchers from outside, the Commission is also starting initiatives that should ease their entry into the EU for scientific purposes (see *Commission proposes a fast track 'scientific visa'*).

Is there life after a fellowship?

While short stays of several months during PhD training should normally fit harmoniously into the research training programme, longer stays abroad are often overshadowed by the nagging question, "What's next?" Often at least part of the answer to this question lies in the choice of the host institution itself. Opportunities for further career development can vary greatly between different institutions, depending on their financial situation and their general attitude towards issues such as complementary training, conference attendance or the degree of independence that visiting research fellows should enjoy. A wrong choice at an early

Young researchers' mobility on the agenda

stage can turn out to be detrimental for one's entire career.

Even if the host is chosen carefully, early career researchers are often left in an unclear situation after a longer period of time spent abroad. A significant amount of human capital is currently wasted due to the lack of attractive career opportunities on a long-term basis, be it in the public or the private sector (although there are significant national variations). The value of international and/or intersectorial mobility is often not appropriately recognised when it comes to reintegration and to career advancement. On the contrary, a mobile researcher often loses contact with the research structure of her or his home country, which can make reintegration rather difficult. These problems are particularly amplified in countries with recruitment procedures that strongly favour local applicants, or candidates having close ties with local staff.

To respond to this situation, a 'code of conduct for the recruitment of researchers', based on best

practice, is currently being developed by the Commission in collaboration with other stakeholders. The objective is to create a more transparent, open, equal and internationally accepted system of recruitment, which will make it easier for researchers from outside the country to compete with the local researcher community.

If implemented widely, such a code of conduct could greatly help in overcoming the existing disadvantages for mobile researchers in the scientific employment market. However, it remains to be seen to what extent local recruitment committees will follow the guidelines given by such a code. Making adherence to the code a prerequisite for EC funding could be one way to ensure the effectiveness of the measure.

Another way to facilitate the reintegration of mobile researchers is with special return grants and reintegration measures. A number of funding organizations now offer such opportunities, but to produce the desired results they need to be more flexible and promoted more globally.

Research cannot always be planned years in advance, and funding schemes should also give fellows the chance to follow up opportunities that present themselves at short notice. A good example of this is the Human Frontiers Science Program's long-term fellowship scheme, in which fellows can postpone their return after the initial fellowship by up to two years without losing their eligibility for the return phase. The Marie Curie European Reintegration Grants are more restrictive in this respect, asking fellows to apply for the return grant, at the latest, six months before the end of the initial fellowship and giving them just enough time to wrap up their ongoing projects before starting the reintegration phase.

Outlook

To implement the decision of the 2002 European Council meeting in Barcelona for a significant increase in the R&D investment in Europe, particular attention needs to be paid to the researchers who are expected to be the pillars of this effort. At the moment, despite the emphasis on researcher training and mobility, there are still quite a number of problems associated with scientific careers.

It is clear that unless we achieve a more regular investment in research in most of the national states in combination with a clear long-term vision, career prospects for researchers cannot significantly improve. Better communication

between scientists, policy makers, politicians and the public can help towards demonstrating the importance of science in a knowledge-based economy and enhance the attractiveness and prospects for research careers. Establishing a clear professional identity for researchers will help in this direction, and also in addressing the large number of administrative problems including the burning issue of transferability of social rights for mobile researchers. The EC's initiative to create a European Researchers Charter, promoting a framework for the career management and employment prospects of researchers is certainly a step in the right direction.

There is a growing tendency to expect that all problems will be resolved at European level, however, often forgetting the responsibility of the national and regional authorities. Given that 94% of the non-military research budget of the EU comes from the member states (where also the source of many difficulties lies), it is clear that a combination of European initiatives and co-

ordinated actions at the national level is the only way to move forward.

Links

Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary
<http://www.m-w.com>

Early Stage Researcher Mobility – Meeting the Challenges and Promoting Best Practice
www.mariecurie.org/esrm2004

Marie Curie Fellowship Association
<http://www.mariecurie.org>

Euroscience
<http://www.euroscience.org>

Eurodoc
<http://www.eurodoc.net>

Postgraduates International (PI-net)
<http://www.postgrad.org>

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